

A Study of Budgetary Control

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ABSTRACT:

Budgetary control is a system of controlling costs through preparation of budgets. Budgeting is thus only a part of the budgetary control. According to CIMA London, “Budgetary control is the establishment of budget relating to the responsibilities of executives of a policy and the continuous comparison of the actual results with budgeted results, either to secure by individual action the objective of the policy or to provide a basis for its revision.”

One of the primary function of management is to plan for the future and to ensure that plans are put into action. One way of planning is through budgets. A budget is merely a plan relating to a period of time, expressed in quantitative terms. In the business world, a budget is a formal budgeting control procedures provide invaluable aid for scientific management.

Keywords: Budgetary Control, Financial Management, Budget, cost

1. INTRODUCTION:

For the preparation of this Research Paper on budgetary control it is necessary to know the concept of budgetary control. Budgetary control is very wide concept and it is help to achieve the targets of organization and also to managerial control. Managerial Control become essential in case of Public and Private Companies which are run by hired managerial personnel with little interest in the result of such enterprises. The proprietor thinks of device which may encourage the management to work greater care and caution to serve the interest of all by optimizing the use of

investment in the form of man, money, machines. Budgets is one such device which help the management to understand the business program in their right perspective and take to achieve the business objective.

Budgeting means planning for future. It involves the preparation of departmental budgets and budgetary control and related issues. The budgetary control concern with management of business activities with the help of budgets. This way, budgets serves as a control device. It helps to plan the policy of business. It can control the function so that the best possible results may be obtained. It is well recognized that budget are among the essential tools of management of any organization unlike other management aids, budgets are made use of practically by all functionaries in the organization. Budgets not only reflect the plan of action for different levels of management but are also useful to monitor various activates and initiate mid-course corrective actions. Budgets just do not reduce the managerial function to a mere formula but aids as a managerial tool.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

“A careful investigation or enquiry especially through search for new facts in any branch of knowledge.”

The design of the research Paper popularly known as the "research design". Research design is a basis of framework, which provides guideline for the rest of research process. It is the map of blue print according to which, the research is to be conducted. The research design specifies the method of study. There are three basic types of research design via exploratory, descriptive and environmental.

A research design helps to define the problem, method of data collection and analysis, time and requirement for the Research Paper to estimate the expenses to be incurred. It is purely and simply the framework or plan for a study that guides data collection. This Research Paper based descriptive and statistical research design.

I have prepared Research Paper report on process costing. For this purpose various information are require to collect these information are collect by various.

Methodology means the method use for the collection of data preparation of Research Paper report.

Importance of Research: -

- New knowledge.
- Social welfare and progress
- Development of science
- Acts as a basis for govt. policies
- Control over unhealthy trends
- Collection of information the economic and social structure of the nation information about social relationship.

Limitations of research: -

- Lack of confidence
- Absence of code of conduct
- Lack of resources
- Overlapping the information
- Lack of scientific trends, lack of interaction
- Problem of coordination and inefficient library and information system.

3.DATA COLLECTION

Information can be divided into two parts primary and secondary data, depending upon the source of the information. Following methods were used for the data collection from the Ashirwad Enterprises..For the preparation of Research Paperreport on process costing. In this study two types of data are considered.

Primary Data –

Primary data used in research originally obtained through surveys, interviews and direct observation. I was collected primary data related to the Research Paper from the discussion and interaction with the senior employees and executives in the

organization.

Secondary Data –

Secondary data, which is obtained through published sources, but it is also more current and more relevant to the research Paper. I was collected secondary data from the documents, which were in printed forms like annual reports, reference books based on cost and works accounting and through websites.

In this study data have been collect from the various secondary Data-

- Annual Report
- Internet
- Books

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

ASHIRWAD ENTERPRISES - PRODUCTION BUDGET

Particulars	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18
Expected Sales(Units)	42000	45000	50000
Add – Closing Stock	22000	13750	10000
Total	64000	58750	60000
Less – Opening Stock	15500	22000	13750
Budgeted Production (Units)	48500	36750	46250

Interpretation:

The material purchase budget showed the expected purchase of material. In the year 2015-16 material required for the production is 66,500 units, in the year of 2016-17 46,750 units. And in the year of 2017-18 is 54750 units.

COST OF PRODUCTION BUDGET

Particulars	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18
Direct Material	665000	467500	547500
Direct Labour	400000	320000	405000
Add- Production Overheads	450000	356750	577800
Fixed Variable	300000	255000	325000
Cost of Production (Rs.)	1815000	1399250	1855300

Interpretation:

The cost of production budget shows estimated cost of production of boxes. In the year 2015-16 estimated cost incurred on production is Rs.18, 15,000/-. In the year 2016-17 is Rs.13, 99,250/- And in the year 2017-18 is Rs.18, 55,300/-.

CASH BUDGET

	Particulars	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18
(A)	Opening Balance	500000	470000	111250
(B)	Receipts -			
	Sales	1985000	1544500	2056700
	Total	2485000	2014500	2167950
(C)	Payments -			
	Material	665000	467500	547500
	Labour	400000	320000	405000
	Production Overheads	750000	611750	902800
	Selling Overheads	50000	34000	46000
	Purchased of Machinery	150000	-	-
	Total	2015000	1433250	1901300
(D)	Closing Balance	470000	111250	266650

Interpretation:

In this cash budget opening balance of year 2015-16 is Rs. 5,00,000/-. in the year 2016-17 is Rs. 4,70,000/-. And in the year 2017-18 is Rs. 1, 11,250/-. All receipts of year 2015-16, 2016-17 & 2017-18 is Rs. 19, 85000/-, Rs. 15, 44,500/- &Rs. 20, 56,700/- respectively. All payments of year 2015-16, 2016-17 & 2017-18 is Rs. 20, 15000/-, Rs. 14, 33,250/- &Rs. 19, 01,300/- respectively. And estimated closing balance of year 2015-16, 2016-17 & 2017-18 is Rs. 4,70,000/-, 1,11,250/- &Rs. 2,66,650/- respectively.

5.FINDINGS

1. Actual budgetary system established in Ashirwad Enterprises.
2. Budgets were prepared on yearly basis.
3. Standards are set for the execution of budgets.

For achieving budgeted figure they use following budgetary techniques

A. Relating to Sales

- Sales order have generated when production work is in progress. Sales budget prepared on the basis of production budget and production budget is prepared on the basis of estimated sales. Means their basic sales budget is fixed and equal with production budget.

B. Relating to Purchase

- Purchase budget has been prepared with view of sales and production budgets. Purchase budgets prepared on quantitative terms. They not consider prices. There is no any budgetary control system established for purchase budgets. Because through they prepare purchase budget on the basis of production and sales, it hasn't fixed. If they have received their required material in low prices with high quality compared to previous purchase, they purchased it in large quantity.

C. Comparison

- The comparison between budget and actual made daily and on-line, hence, they can remove variances immediately and also understand the reason thereof as already stated above.
- The production budget show the budgeted production of product. In the year 2015-16 budgeted production of boxes is 48,500units. In the year of 2016-17 budgeted production is 36,750units and in the year of 2017-18 budgeted production is 46,250 units.
- The material purchase budget shown the expected purchase of material. In the year 2015-16 material required for the production is 66,500 units, in the year of 2016-17 46,750 units. And in the year of 2017-18 is 54750 units.

6. SUGGESTIONS

1. Preparation, implementation, overview and all budget related matter carried out by manager. Here delegation of authority and responsibility is necessary for proper utilization of budgetary control.
2. Production budget and sales budget should not be same. These two are separate concepts thoughts correlated. If those will separately consider. We can properly fixed or targets, maximize sales targets, which affects in profit as favorable positions and also in maximization.
3. Capital expenditure budget should also have been prepared by the industry, for setting contingent liabilities.
4. They should have to add various labour incentive and welfare schemes for increasing productivity of labour which helps in proper implementation in targets and maintenance of the quality of products.
5. Proper implementation of budget is necessary. After the preparation of the budget, it must be properly implemented.
6. In order to make budgetary control system effective in a concern, proper recording of various operations such as purchase, sales, production etc.

7. CONCLUSION

Ashirwad Enterprises. Is a small scale industry. Though it has a self-budgetary control system. From the discussion with the manner, I understand that, they always achieved their target with successfully. Prices are based on full cost plus profit method. Hence, stability in prices does not maintained by them, which adversely effect on volume of sales. Purchase activity carried out when 40% inventory in hand, here the question of blockage of capital in unnecessary inventory avoided. Sales budget and production budget are interrelated term used by them as a same manner. Unnecessary labor charges avoided, when there is no any work load. Proper judgment of labour cost achieved by them.

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